

figure panel	data type	location	accession	name_supplementary_data	data format
1A	mass_spectrometry	ProteomeXChange	PXD043333	Raw MS data	text; raw data
3E	mass_spectrometry	ProteomeXChange	PXD048760	Raw MS data	text; raw data
1A	mass_spectrometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	MassSpec_MUTZ3_EVI1vslgG.txt	text
1B & S1C	mass_spectrometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	MassSpec_MUTZ3_EVI1vslgG_Clusters.txt	text
S1E	mass_spectrometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	MassSpec_NFS78_BiotagvsNoBiotag.txt; MassSpec_NFS78_BiotagvsNoBiotag_designTable.xlsx	text & xlsx
3E	mass_spectrometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	MassSpec_MUTZ3_PLDLSvsPLASS_DIA_results[.xlsx&csv]; MassSpec_MUTZ3_PLDLSvsPLASS_DIA_DesignTable.csv	csv & xlsx
1C, 1E, S2B, 3F, 3G, S6B	chip_seq	GEO	GSE236010	see GEO_perfigure	bigwig, narrowpeak and fastq
	chip_seq	github*	Github & Geo	chipseq-corrplots/CTBP_Mut3_peaks.narrowPeak; chipseq-corrplots/EVI1_Mut3_peaks.narrowPeak	narrowPeak
3G	chip_seq	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	ChIPseq_EVI1_2747.bigwig	bigwig
1D, S3A	chip_seq	github*	Github	chipseq-corrplots/counts_CTBP2peaks.txt; chipseq-corrplots/counts_EVI1peaks.txt	text
	chip_seq	github*	Github	chipseq-corrplots/heatmaps_corr.RMD	.RMD
S6A, S6C	chip_seq	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	DiffBind_20230816_PLASSvsPLDLS_CTBP2.csv	csv
S6E	chip_seq	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	CTBP2UntreatedTrackannot_PeaksToGenes.txt	tsv
S6B	chip_seq	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	ChIPseq_DiffBind_IndPLDLS_EVI1_CTBP2.zip	zipped folder [csv files]
S6C	rna_seq	GEO	GSE236010	Raw FASTQ files and quant.sf	various
	rna_seq	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	deseq2_apeGLMLog2FC_PLDLSvsPLASS.txt	text
2A, 3A	alphafold_predicted_structures	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	AlphaFold_Predictions.zip	zipped_folder [pdb, txt and fasta files]
S5B	alphafold_predicted_structures	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	AlphaFold_Predictions_PLDLSProteome.zip	zipped_folder [pdb, txt and fasta files]
2B	chimerax_python_scripts	github*	Github	alphafold_quantResidues/AlphaFold_python_cmds_chimerax_*.py	.py script
	chimerax_r_scripts	github*	Github	alphafold_quantResidues/alphafold_quant_int_res_gitversion.rmd	.RMD
	chimerax_contacts	github*	Github	alphafold_quantResidues/chimerax_contacts_*.txt	text
4C, 5B	flow_cytometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	FlowCytometry_Gating.pdf	PDF
5C, 5F, S7C, S7D	flow_cytometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	FlowCytometry_SB1690_MixExperiments_FrequencyTables.xlsx	xlsx
5D, S7B	flow_cytometry	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	FlowCytometry_MUTZ3_MixExp_GatingAndFrequencies.zip	zipped_folder [pdf and csv files]
5H	luciferase_outgrowth	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	LuciferaseSize_MUTZ3_ScaffoldMice.xlsx	.xlsx
S2J, S7A	cell_counts	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	cell_counts.zip	zipped_folder [.pfzx & .csv & .pdf]
3D, S1A, S1B, S2J, S3C, S4E	western_blot	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	WesternBlots_full.pdf	PDF
2D, 2E, S4C, S4D, 3C	mappit_data	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	mappit.zip	zipped_folder [.pfzx & .xlsx]
S4B	mappit_data	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	MAPPIT_CTBP2_Mutants.zip	zipped_folder [.pfzx & .csv & .pdf]
2F, 4B, 5A	colony_assay	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	colony_assays.zip	zipped_folder [.pfzx & .csv]
S5A	protein_alignments	ZENODO	10.5281/zenodo.10650341	ProteinAlignment_PLDLS_[PLDLS_35AA.fasta/FullProteinSeqs.fasta]	.fasta
S5A, S5B	protein_alignments	github*	Github	PLDLS_ProteinAlignment	.RMD & various other formats

*all github data is also uploaded in 1 ZIP file in this repository called GITHUB.zip